

WORK MOTIVATION CONSTRUCTS AMONG BARANGAY DISASTER RISK REDUCTION AND MANAGEMENT COUNCIL VOLUNTEERS**Carin, Leslie Ann C.¹****Escote, Donah May B.²****Hormachuelos, Angelika T.³****Makiwag, Sharelyn U.⁴****Taporoc, Remy S.⁵**

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ABSTRACT

Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC) volunteers play an essential role in community safety and disaster preparedness, yet limited research has been conducted to understand what drives their commitment and sustained engagement in this high-stakes field. Recognizing the need to support these volunteers, this study seeks to identify the core motivators that encourage them to remain active in disaster management efforts. The study is non-experimental quantitative design utilizing Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) to uncover the primary motivational dimensions. Data were gathered from 150 BDRRMC volunteers using a structured questionnaire. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity were conducted to assess the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

The survey results identified four key dimensions of motivation among BDRRMC volunteers: Personal Development and Achievement, Social and Career Development, Values and Purpose Alignment, and Gratitude and Appreciation. These dimensions provide a framework for understanding and enhancing the factors that drive volunteer engagement within BDRRMCs, offering practical insights for increasing volunteer retention and motivation in community-based disaster management initiatives.

Keywords:

Work Motivation, BDRRMC, Volunteers, Personal Development and Achievement, Social and Career Development, Values and Purpose Alignment, Gratitude and Appreciation

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is among the most disaster-prone countries globally, ranking high in vulnerability due to its geographical location and socio-economic conditions. With an average of 20 typhoons annually, alongside risks of earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, and flooding, the need for robust disaster management strategies is critical (Asian Development Bank, 2019). The involvement of Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (BDRRMC) volunteers has been pivotal, as these community-based groups play a crucial role in early warning systems, disaster preparedness, and post-disaster recovery (Antonio, 2018).

Volunteerism is a cornerstone of disaster response in the Philippines, with Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Councils (BDRRMCs) playing an integral role. Comprised largely of local volunteers, BDRRMCs facilitate preparedness, response, and recovery efforts in barangays—the smallest administrative divisions in the country. These councils embody community-led approaches to disaster management, leveraging local knowledge and social networks for swift and effective action (United Nations Volunteers, 2024).

The motivation of these volunteers is essential to the effectiveness of BDRRMCs. Motivated individuals are more likely to engage in tasks that ensure community safety and disaster preparedness, while also building long-term resilience. Despite the voluntary nature of this work, many of these volunteers demonstrate dedication to their roles, often under difficult and hazardous conditions. Thus, understanding the underlying work motivation

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constructs is crucial in enhancing volunteer engagement and ensuring sustainable disaster risk management programs (Santos et al., 2020).

Despite the crucial role these volunteers play in community safety and disaster preparedness, there has been limited understanding of what drives their sustained involvement and commitment.

OBJECTIVES

This study was conducted to determine the dimensions of work motivation among Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC) volunteers.

METHODOLOGY

The respondents of this study were volunteers from several Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Councils. A total of 150 respondents participated by completing an online survey and a printed questionnaire, which served as the research instrument for this study. The researchers adapted several statements from multiple survey questionnaires and modified them to better align with the objectives of this study. The respondents were asked to assess their motivation for volunteering in their respective Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Councils using a 5-point Likert scale (5=always, 1=never) corresponding to the statements in the questionnaire.

The data gathered were subjected to Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) to identify the factors that motivate respondents to volunteer in their Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Councils. Factor analysis is a statistical technique that combines a group of variables associated with one common underlying factor. According to Taherdoost, Sahibuddin, & Jalaliyoon, (2022), exploratory factor analysis involves five implementation steps. These significant steps are Evaluation of Data Suitability for EFA, Factor Extraction Method, Factor Retention Method, Selection of Rotational Method, and Interpretation and Labeling.

In this study, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity were conducted to assess whether the respondent data were adequate and suitable for factor analysis. Additionally, a Scree Plot was used to help determine the number of factors or components to extract and retain for the analysis. The retained factors were then organized, labeled, and interpreted.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This section consists of the literature review that supported the study and presented according to the objectives of the study in relation to the work motivation among BDRRMC Volunteers.

Personal Development and Achievement. The capabilities of volunteers are highly valued especially in disaster response, and recognizing their contributions can enhance their motivation (Jaime et al., 2023). BDRRMC Volunteers motivated by the personal growth and a sense of achievement they get from engaging in volunteering works. The experience also facilitated self-discovery, enabling volunteers to explore their strengths and set personal development goals, thus building confidence. Additionally, Turk et al. (2022) highlighted that volunteering offers a platform for self-growth by allowing individuals to reshape their identities through meaningful connections and a sense of community. These enabling environments encourage individuals to stretch beyond their current experiences and comfort zones, pushing them to discover new aspects of themselves and establish a greater sense of purpose and achievement. Such experiences also improve well-being by cultivating personal fulfillment and resilience.

Social and Career Development. Volunteering provides a structured environment for career exploration, allowing individuals to try out various roles, gain practical experience, and build employability by developing new skills and expanding professional networks. This aligns with findings by Turk et al. (2022), who emphasize that volunteering facilitates meaningful social connections with individuals from diverse backgrounds, age groups, and professions. These interactions enable BDRRMC Volunteers to broaden their perspectives, foster inclusivity, and develop a deeper sense of empathy and social awareness.

The study conducted by AlAmpAy (2019) showed that local partners' capacity and active engagement impact volunteer motivation and the rate of learning and innovation. It provides volunteers with practical experience, skills, and connections that may help them transition to desired employment or explore career paths. Additionally, volunteering provides a unique opportunity for hands-on career exploration without requiring a long-term commitment. This exposure aids in career decision-making by allowing individuals to assess different fields firsthand. As Turk et al. (2022) indicate, for volunteers from different cultural backgrounds, these

experiences facilitate cultural exchange and integration, enriching the community while fostering a strong sense of belonging. Through volunteering, individuals often discover new strengths, develop confidence, and experience continuous personal growth.

Values and Purpose Alignment. The alignment of volunteer tasks with personal values and beliefs significantly contributes to volunteer motivation. According to Jr. (2023), motivations such as personal fulfillment, the desire to create a positive impact, and a sense of responsibility toward others resonate deeply with the principles of ecological spirituality. For BDRRMC volunteers, the desire to apply their specific skills to help their communities is a significant motivator, shaping their commitment and effectiveness in disaster response (Ganoe et al., 2023). Furthermore, autonomy or having the freedom to make choices in how volunteering activities are carried out, is another significant motivator. This autonomy is significantly linked to positive motivation and can enhance the wellbeing of BDRRMC volunteers (De Clerck et al., 2022). However, the ability to express their values through volunteering and the satisfaction of knowing that their service is a true expression of those values is also a significant motivator (Carvalho et al., 2024). Lastly, some BDRRMC volunteers see their work as a way to build personal discipline and maintain focus, highlighting that volunteer experiences can contribute to the enhancement of skills that are valuable not only in community service but also in personal and professional contexts (Gamit & Vallespin, 2023).

Gratitude and Appreciation. Creating change requires a large network of people working together to get the job done. Volunteers are a key part of organizations, and they deserve to be appreciated for all their enthusiasm and hard work. Most volunteers devote their time to a nonprofit because they're motivated by the cause or interested in the organization's work. To sustain that dedication and motivation, it's important to implement dedicated systems for recognizing your volunteers to effectively show your thanks (Volunteer Match, 2023).

Positive feedback validates volunteers' contributions and fosters a sense of belonging within the organization, encouraging further engagement. For BDRRMC volunteers, recognition and appreciation are key to motivating them to continue their service in disaster relief. However, engagement in disaster situations can be challenging, as many individuals are involved in providing support to survivors. As primary front-liners in a crisis, these responders deserve recognition, which includes addressing potential gaps in their roles. Evaluating factors such as knowledge, tools, equipment, and training helps expedite their skill development, fostering more effective engagement (Abellare et al., 2024).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Presented in this section is the analysis and interpretation of the consolidated data.

Table 1. KMO and Barlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.732
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1645.393
	Df	435
	Sig.	.000

Further, Barlett's Test of Sphericity with a chi-square value of 3011.468, degrees of freedom (df) value of 435, and p-value of .000 ($p < 0.05$) indicates that the correlation matrix is significantly different from the identity matrix, supporting the presence of underlying factors, hence, confirming that the sample used is suitable for the study and that factor analysis is appropriate as the treatment to utilize as the analytical tool. Overall, the results indicate that the sampling size employed in this study is sufficient to proceed to factor analysis.

Table 2. Total Variance Explained

		Extractions Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotations Sums of Squared Loading		
	Eigenvalues	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
Factor 1	13.319	13.319	44.395	44.395	5.900	19.666	19.666
Factor 2	1.965	1.965	6.550	50.945	5.288	17.628	37.293
Factor 3	1.597	1.597	5.322	56.268	4.033	13.443	50.737
Factor 4	1.206	1.206	4.019	60.287	2.865	9.550	60.287

By examining the variance percentage in the Total Variance Explained Table, we can observe that the first factor explains 19.666% of the total variance, indicating that it accounts for a significant portion of the variability in the dataset. The second factor explains 17.628% of the variance, the third factor explains 13.443%, and the fourth factor explains 9.550%. Therefore, the first factor contributes the most to explaining the variance, while the fourth factor has the smallest impact.

The four identified factors collectively account for a total variance of 60.287%, as indicated in the table. This means that these four factors capture the majority of the underlying variation in the dataset, providing a meaningful representation of the data's structure.

The Rotated Component Matrix contains twenty-six items categorized into four dimensions. The table indicates that four items were excluded from this categorization. These four items were removed from the model due to their validity issues and low commonalities. As suggested by Hair et al., (2022), once all the significant loadings and cross-loading issues have been identified and the commonalities examined, the researcher may proceed to evaluate each variable for potential deletion based on its overall contribution to the study's objectives and commonality index.

The scree plot was utilized to graphically determine the number of constructs influencing the motivation of BDRRM Volunteers. As shown in Figure 1, the point above the debris or break, not including the break itself, indicates the number of factors that are to be retained. Examining the Scree plot and eigenvalues revealed a departure from linearity, which coincided with a 4-factor result. The Scree Test suggests that there are four factors in the analysed data.

Figure 1. Scree Plot

Personal Development and Achievement. Table 3 shows the ten items that fall under the first dimension, the personal development and achievement, and their corresponding loading coefficients. As shown, the item 'Receiving certificates and awards motivates me' obtained the highest loading coefficient of 0.717. The item 'I enjoy the challenges that comes with the task' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.711. The item 'It allows me to develop my leadership skills' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.705. The item 'Volunteering let me learn things through direct hands-on experience' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.702. The item 'I feel the sense of accountability and responsibility' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.670.

Meanwhile, the item 'I can explore my own strengths' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.668. The item 'I volunteer because I believe in the mission and values of the organization' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.631. The item 'I can learn how to deal with a variety of people' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.597. The item 'I feel a sense of personal achievement when I volunteer' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.568. The item 'The training provided by the BDRRMC is very useful' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.540.

These findings highlight that factor related to personal development, such as receiving certificates and awards, serve as powerful motivators, providing a sense of accomplishment and fulfillment. The challenges encountered in various tasks offer valuable opportunities to enhance leadership skills and promote personal growth. It also shows that through volunteering allow individuals to learn through hands-on experience. It nurtures a sense of accountability and responsibility while enabling personal strengths to be explored. Additionally, the training offered by the BDRRMC proves to be highly beneficial, providing volunteers with essential practical knowledge and skills.

These motivations highlight how volunteering can contribute to personal development and achievement. The capabilities of volunteers are highly valued especially in disaster response, and recognizing their contributions can enhance their motivation (Jaime et al., 2023). Additionally, Turk et al. (2022) highlighted that volunteering offers a platform for self-growth by allowing individuals to reshape their identities through meaningful connections and a sense of community. These enabling environments encourage individuals to stretch beyond their current experiences and comfort zones, pushing them to discover new aspects of themselves and establish a greater sense of purpose and achievement. Such experiences also improve well-being by cultivating personal fulfillment and resilience.

Table 3. Rotated matrix with Group of Attributes under Personal Development and Achievement

Item	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
18	Receiving certificates and awards motivates me.	0.717	Personal Development and Achievement
17	I enjoy the challenges that comes with the task.	0.711	
19	It allows me to develop my leadership skills.	0.705	
9	Volunteering let me learn things through direct hands-on experience.	0.702	
27	I feel the sense of accountability and responsibility.	0.670	
12	I can explore my own strengths.	0.668	
26	I volunteer because I believe in the mission and values of the organization.	0.631	
10	I can learn how to deal with a variety of people.	0.597	
16	I feel a sense of personal achievement when I volunteer.	0.568	
20	The training provided by the BDRRMC is very much useful.	0.540	

Social and Career Enhancement. Table 4 shows eight items that fall under the second dimension, social and career enhancement, and the corresponding loading coefficients. As shown in the item 'Through volunteering, I can build a network and meet new people,' it obtained the highest loading coefficient of 0.726. The item 'Volunteering allows me to gain a new perspective on things' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.720. The item 'Through volunteering, I feel a sense of belongingness' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.716. Concurrently, the item 'Volunteering can help me to be in a place where I would like to work' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.694. The item 'Volunteering increases my self-esteem' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.670. The item 'Volunteering allows me to explore different career options' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.664. The item 'I am concerned about the safety of my community' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.633. The last item, 'No matter how bad I've been feeling, volunteering helps me forget about it,' obtained a loading coefficient of 0.600.

The Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC) volunteers perceive that volunteering can serve as a social platform for meeting new people and forming meaningful connections. It has social benefits and networking opportunities. By working alongside professionals in disaster management, local government officials, and NGOs, volunteers can expand their network, which may open doors for future job opportunities, particularly in fields related to public safety, environmental management, or community development. Volunteering exposes them to new experiences, helping them become more empathetic or open-minded. It fulfills their sense of belonging and promotes connectedness and community engagement. Volunteerism also psychologically impacts them as it allows them to boost their mood and distract them from personal struggles. Self-worth is also recognized by the Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC) volunteers. They feel accomplished by volunteering, which allows them to make a positive impact and receive social recognition for their contributions. These volunteers are trained in various disaster management techniques, such as first aid, search and rescue, and crisis communication. These skills are transferable to various fields, including healthcare, emergency services, and even management roles. Working in a team during disaster preparedness exercises and actual events helps build leadership skills, as volunteers may be tasked with managing groups of people. This experience can be valuable for those aiming for leadership positions in their professional lives. Often times they face unpredictable situations, which enhances their adaptability and problem-solving abilities. Being exposed to high-pressure environments helps these individuals become more resourceful and resilient, and employers highly value these traits.

Volunteers commit themselves to being part of the Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC) to satisfy different psychological needs, such as social, esteem, and career. The study conducted by AlAmpAy et al., (2019) showed that local partners' capacity and active engagement impact volunteers' motivation and the rate of learning and innovation. It provides volunteers with practical experience, skills, and connections that may help them transition to desired employment or explore career paths. Volunteering provides hands-on exposure to various fields and careers, allowing the volunteers to test out different work areas in a low-risk environment. Many people use volunteering to explore new career directions or interests. Moreover, Rosario (2022) mentioned in his study that there is a positive social impact of volunteerism which has been recognized globally. Volunteerism has a significant impact on economic, social welfare, and individual levels. The social, economic, and individual benefits of volunteerism are undeniable. On the social level, volunteering strengthens communities and supports those in need. Economically, it contributes to cost savings and drives productivity in both the non-profit and public sectors. For individuals, volunteering offers personal development, career growth, and a sense of fulfillment that enhances overall well-being.

Table 4. Rotated Matrix with Group under Social and Career Enhancement

Item	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
5	Through volunteering, I can build a network and meet new people.	0.726	Social and Career Enhancement
7	Volunteering allows me to gain a new perspective on things.	0.720	
11	Through volunteering, I feel a sense of belongingness.	0.716	
1	Volunteering can help me to be in a place where I would like to work.	0.694	
6	Volunteering increases my self-esteem.	0.670	
8	Volunteering allows me to explore different career options.	0.664	
3	I am concerned about the safety of my community.	0.633	
4	No matter how bad I've been feeling, volunteering helps me to forget about it.	0.600	

Values and Purpose Alignment. Table 5 displays the five items that fall under the third dimension, the value and purpose alignment, along with their corresponding loading coefficients. The item, "I feel like I'm doing something worthwhile" has the highest loading coefficient of 0.715. The item, "I can bring my skills and expertise through volunteering" has a loading coefficient of 0.637. Another significant item is, "I feel the sense of autonomy and control over my volunteer task," which obtained a loading coefficient of 0.619. The item, "It aligns with my personal values and beliefs" shows a loading coefficient of 0.557. Lastly, the item, "It helps me to become more disciplined and focused" obtained a loading coefficient of 0.502.

The BDRRMC volunteers demonstrate high motivation when their work aligns with their values, skills, and sense of purpose. This alignment not only leads to effective volunteerism but also to personal fulfillment and growth, which are crucial aspects of volunteer motivation. This finding, in line with existing literature, underscores that values and purpose alignment are significant motivators for volunteering.

A strong sense of purpose and meaningful contribution are among the significant indicators that motivate the volunteers of the BDRRMC to engage in volunteer work. This is supported by the research of Caraveo (2022) and Liu et al., (2018), which explored the psychological and personal development aspects linked to participation in volunteer activities. Their findings supported the idea that involvement in volunteering activities contributes significantly to individuals' perceived sense of purpose. For BDRRMC volunteers, the desire to apply their specific skills to help their communities is a significant motivator, shaping their commitment and effectiveness in disaster response (Ganoë et al., 2023). Furthermore, autonomy or having the freedom to make choices in how volunteering activities are carried out, is another significant motivator. This autonomy is significantly linked to positive motivation and can enhance the wellbeing of BDRRMC volunteers (De Clerck et al., 2022). The ability to express their values through volunteering and the satisfaction of knowing that their service is a true expression of those values is also a significant motivator (Carvalho et al., 2024). Lastly, some BDRRMC volunteers see their work as a way to build personal discipline and maintain focus, highlighting that volunteer experiences can contribute to the enhancement of skills that are valuable not only in community service but also in personal and professional contexts (Gamit & Vallespin, 2023).

Table 5. Rotated Matrix with Group Attributes under Values and Purpose Alignment

Item	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimensions
13	I feel like I'm doing something worthwhile.	0.715	Values and Purpose Alignment
14	I can bring my skills and expertise through volunteering.	0.637	
25	I feel the sense of autonomy and control over my volunteer task.	0.619	
22	It aligns with my personal values and beliefs.	0.557	
28	It helps me to become more disciplined and focused.	0.502	

Gratitude and Appreciation. Table 6 shows three items categorized under the fourth dimension, Gratitude and Appreciation, along with their respective loading coefficients. The item, "I volunteer to repay the support I received from others in the past," achieved the highest loading coefficient of 0.740, indicating that a strong sense of reciprocity drives many volunteers. Meanwhile, the item "I feel motivated when I receive verbal praise from my peers" shows a loading coefficient of 0.676, highlighting the role of social recognition as a motivating factor. Lastly, the item "I volunteer because of the trust placed in me" obtained a loading coefficient of 0.533. This shows that trust-based responsibility not only promotes personal growth but also enhances volunteer satisfaction, creating a positive cycle of motivation and accountability.

The gratitude and appreciation received by volunteers motivated BDRRM to continue developing their commitment and maintain their roles as volunteers. Acts of gratitude, such as verbal recognition or expressions of trust, validate their efforts and reinforce their sense of purpose. These gestures build morale and create a supporting environment that encourages volunteers to remain dedicated to their responsibilities.

Creating change requires a large network of people working together to get the job done. Volunteers are a key part of organizations, and they deserve to be appreciated for all their enthusiasm and hard work. Most volunteers devote their time to a nonprofit because they're motivated by the cause or interested in the organization's work. To sustain that dedication and motivation, it's important to implement dedicated systems for recognizing your volunteers to effectively show your thanks (Volunteer Match, 2023).

Positive feedback validates volunteers' contributions and fosters a sense of belonging within the organization, encouraging further engagement. For BDRRMC volunteers, recognition and appreciation are key to motivating them to continue their service in disaster relief. However, engagement in disaster situations can be challenging, as many individuals are involved in providing support to survivors. As primary front-liners in a crisis, these responders deserve recognition, which includes addressing potential gaps in their roles. Evaluating factors such as knowledge, tools, equipment, and training helps expedite their skill development, fostering more effective engagement (Abellare et al., 2024).

Table 6. Rotated Matrix with Group Attributes under Gratitude and Appreciation

Item	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
Item 30	I volunteer to repay the support I received from others in the past.	0.740	Gratitude and Appreciation
Item 15	I feel motivated when I receive verbal praise from my peers.	0.676	
Item 29	I volunteer because of the trust placed in me.	0.533	

Framework Developed Based on Findings

This study focused on measuring and analyzing the underlying factors that influence the work motivation model among Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC) volunteers. Figure 1 illustrates the framework developed based on the findings in this study. As shown, it has four dimensions of work motivation model, which are Personal Development and Achievement, Social and Career Development, Values and Purpose Alignment, and Gratitude and Appreciation.

Figure 2. The Dimensions that Influence the Work Motivation of BDRRMC Volunteers

CONCLUSION

The study examined the key motivations that influence Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC) Volunteers to participate in disaster management and response efforts. Through exploratory factor analysis, it identified four motivational dimensions: personal development and achievement, social and career development, values and purpose alignment, and gratitude and appreciation. These findings highlighted both intrinsic and extrinsic factors driving volunteerism, such as the significance of recognition, skill enhancement, social networking, alignment with personal values, and reciprocity. Insights from these motivators can help local leaders and policymakers design effective strategies to maintain volunteer engagement, ultimately enhancing the resilience and efficiency of disaster preparedness initiatives.

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